

THEORETICAL BASIS FOR CREATING A MULTILINGUAL ELECTRONIC DICTIONARY OF CHEMICAL TERMS

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Introduction. In the last century, there was a sharp increase in the number of terms, which can be described as a terminological boom, borrowed from J. Lukszin and W. Zmarzer. This trend is unlikely to stop anytime soon. Just as the observed proliferation of terms has occurred at a rapid rate covering various fields of human activity, it has also enabled and facilitated them. For progress to be possible, the underlying idea, be it a new discovery, invention, or innovation, must be expressed, communicated (in the broadest sense of the word), and understood. Otherwise, the idea, regardless of its originality, novelty and ingenuity, has no chance to have any impact on society and will eventually be forgotten. Accordingly, specialized communication, the purpose of which can be defined as "influencing the structure of special knowledge by means of techniques not available in general communication", is very important for the development of any communication. Fields and similar language units often appear in specialized communication.

Main body. Considering the important role of specialized communication, it is necessary to facilitate this process. If specialized communication takes place in the form of text, this undoubtedly complex problem has a clear linguistic aspect, so it is reasonable to expect that linguistics or related disciplines will not only solve the problem, but also contribute to overcoming it. One question that has been and continues to be answered can be broadly stated as follows: How can people be helped to produce and receive specialized texts to convey, understand, and acquire specialized knowledge more easily and accurately? Among the many proposed solutions, terminological dictionaries seem particularly promising. This is not only a respectable tradition of successfully serving in the description of various features of terms, but also their adaptability as specialized language models, flexibility, their scope, the size of which was manifested in the rich variety of already published works. While it is inescapable that great progress has been made in the field of terminologies, there are still hurdles to be overcome and gaps to be filled. One such challenge is to construct terminological dictionaries that accurately represent a system of terms rather than treating individual terms in isolation.

As the title suggests, this article aims to develop a model of a systematic English-Uzbek dictionary of chemical terminology. Although there are many works on terminological dictionaries, systematic dictionaries have received very little attention so far. Nevertheless, the few references that can be found in the literature suggest that they offer benefits to their users by focusing on their unique features, namely the representation of subject area terminology as a network of interrelated terms. comes to the conclusion that it is possible. It is for this reason that today mainly user-oriented lexicography draws attention to issues related to their construction and use. However, their structure also raises questions that are very important to terminology as a field of study and increase their relevance.

The vocabulary model to be developed aims to introduce dictionary users to the most important terms used in the field of chemistry, which will help them not only to understand the basic chemical concepts, but also to see the connection between them, and individual terms, their meanings provides more than a list of riffs and equivalents. In addition, the dictionary helps its users to determine the order of learning terms. As for the target group for which the dictionary can be particularly useful, it includes beginners to English chemical terminology and users who want to learn it or systematically revise it.

Conclusion. This dictionary consists of two main parts. The first part consists of two chapters and describes the theoretical and practical ideas related to the compilation of the dictionary. The second part consists of one chapter and mainly contains the proposed vocabulary,

thus illustrating the principles discussed in the first part. Vocabulary models do not always contain illustrative material for the final vocabulary, and this can be justified. In addition, the vocabulary part is designed to ensure that the model works in practice, not just in theory.

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